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Axiology of Humans and Machines

*Andrzej Grzegorzczak's Method as a Foundation for the
Algorithmization of Law*

Abstract

This article analyzes the possibility of building a coherent, durable system of values for humans and AI systems to cooperate, drawing on Andrzej Grzegorzczak's logical-philosophical concepts. The text diagnoses the crisis of modern cognition, divided between empty formalism and psychological empiricism, and proposes overcoming this division through a rational analysis of objective values. The hierarchy proposed in this paper, grounded in the inalienable dignity of the human person as its overarching axiom, is juxtaposed with the challenges of the algorithmic era. The author argues that Grzegorzczak's method - including his "Decalogue of Reason" and his concepts of absolutist and solidary ethics - provides the necessary semantic framework for evaluating legal norms. Rather than humanizing machines, the proposed paradigm subordinates automated legal systems to principles protecting human dignity, where technology serves to detect logical contradictions, making legal systems resilient to relativism and technocratic reductionism.

Keywords: axiology, artificial intelligence, algorithmic legal systems, Andrzej Grzegorzczak, machine ethics, personalism, formal logic.

Note: *This is not a scientific article in the strict sense, but a programmatic text embedded within a law automation project.*

<https://github.com/galicea/nomos>

1. The Crisis of Modern Cognition

The contemporary world needs a durable system of values that is not subject to political bargaining. Only then can we create a safe space for human-machine cooperation. Thanks to Andrzej Grzegorzczak, we know how to build a system that meets the criteria of mathematical precision while remaining deeply human. Such a paradigm addresses a problem that modern liberalism has largely left unresolved. It prevents a situation in which technology corporations create their own algorithms to optimize human behavior for profit, while helpless states or organizations attempt to enact delayed, incoherent regulations.

Modernity grew out of the conviction that human beings can know the world through reason. Although the Enlightenment did not create the scientific method - its foundations having been laid earlier by Galileo, Bacon, and Newton - it made rationality the primary organizing principle of Western intellectual life. Reason was meant to liberate humanity from superstition, authority, and arbitrary power, and knowledge was to be based on experience and logical analysis.

However, the success of this project came at a price. Empiricism led to the belief that all knowledge originates from the senses. In logic, this resulted in psychologism - the view that logical laws are merely descriptions of how the human mind operates. Logic ceased to be treated as a tool for discovering the objective order of reality and instead became a part of the psychology of cognition.

Gottlob Frege (Frege, 1977) opposed this view. He rejected psychologism and defended the independence of the laws of logic from the human psyche. This was a necessary step for the development of modern mathematical logic, but it simultaneously led to the opposite extreme. Logic was detached from the concrete cognizing subject and reduced to a world of abstract formal structures. The human being ceased to be an active participant in cognition, confined merely to experimentally confirming abstract theories.

In this way, a division characteristic of modernity emerged: on one side,

the formal language of logic; on the other, empirical inquiry, which provides content and semantic grounding. This model proved highly effective in the hard sciences, but it left unresolved the questions of values, meaning, goodness, and the dignity of the person. It is precisely here that the limits of both empiricism and formalism reveal themselves.

2. Andrzej Grzegorzczak's Paradigm

Andrzej Grzegorzczak proposes a way beyond this historical dispute. He does not reject the achievements of analytical philosophy or logical rigor. On the contrary, he treats logic as an indispensable tool for honest thinking. At the same time, he points out that cognition is not a passive process. It consists neither of mechanically gathering data nor of manipulating abstract symbols; rather, it requires active intellectual and moral effort. Man discovers values through a rational analysis of reality, not by arbitrarily establishing them.

It is precisely here that Grzegorzczak's method becomes something more than just another philosophical theory. It combines the precision of analytical thinking with a personalist conviction regarding the central role of the human person. Logic no longer serves to build increasingly complex formal systems, but rather to discover those elements of reality that carry meaning for human life. As Grzegorzczak himself emphasized, formal correctness is not enough for a theory to be considered rational; only those intellectual constructs that remain consistent with the values discovered by reason are truly rational (Grzegorzczak, 1993).

In this sense, his philosophy represents an attempt to preserve the Enlightenment's greatest achievement - trust in reason - while simultaneously overcoming its limitations. Reason is neither a passive mechanism for registering facts nor a sterile symbol-manipulating calculator. It is an active tool for discovering the meaning of the world. "Grzegorzczak's method" can be summarized in two sentences: if we analyze reality rationally, the foundations of our worldview - what we may call values - are discovered. The language of logic allows for the construction of infinitely many theories,

but only those that do not contradict the aforementioned values are rational, not merely formally correct. This summary captures two fundamental pillars of Andrzej Grzegorzczuk's thought:

- **Discovering objective values through rational analysis.** For Grzegorzczuk, values are not a matter of subjective taste or irrational faith. The philosopher explicitly stated that in a mind "cleansed of egoism and subjected to the discipline of logic," the elements of a universal human axiology naturally reveal themselves. Grzegorzczuk rejected the view that man arbitrarily creates values; he believed that we discover them because they are encoded in our existence and constitute the form of our being. These values do not act upon us with causal necessity (determinism) but represent a call to which a free human being must respond. From a cognitive perspective, a rigorous analysis of the mind lays the foundation for objective values.
- **Distinguishing formal correctness from authentic rationality.** The second pillar is the core of his critique of empty formalism. The language of deduction and logic allows the creation of infinitely many theories, meaning one can construct many perfectly formalized systems whose elaboration serves no meaningful purpose. Just because a theory is logically consistent does not mean it is rational in a humanistic sense. Logical thinking "is not merely a mechanical game of formulas" but must touch upon fundamental matters. Detaching the intellect from a sense of value leads to degeneration and alienated speculations. Therefore, Grzegorzczuk rejected closed visions of rationalism, postulating a reason that sees values and can speak about them precisely. Only a theory consistent with intuitions of truth, goodness, and beauty deserves the name of authentic knowledge.

In conclusion, although logic is indeed the indispensable "morality of thought and speech," this tool gains its authentic meaning only when it serves to discover and defend objective, universal values.

3. The Ethics of Thinking

Since logic gains meaning only in the service of values, the question arises: what are the specific habits of thinking? Grzegorzczuk, following Jan Łukasiewicz's formula (Łukasiewicz, 1961), recognizes linguistic precision as a prerequisite for ethical participation in the world. Serious thinking is the opposite of intellectual sloppiness, and logical rigor is not art for art's sake: care for clarity of expression is a form of radical respect for the interlocutor, an acknowledgment of the dignity of their mind. The process of analysis consists of a disciplined selection - moving from superficial observations to constitutive ones, guided by the intuition of values.

Grzegorzczuk translates this postulate into concrete practice in his original "Decalogue of Reason" (Grzegorzczuk, 1993) - ten principles protecting intellectual integrity:

1. You shall not applaud – applause puts self-criticism to sleep and creates uncritical "idols."
2. You shall not jeer – disapproval serves to self-aggrandize at the expense of others.
3. Listen to the content, not the tone – the argument is what matters, not whether the speaker praises.
4. Critique arguments, not persons – avoid ad personam attacks.
5. Do not flatter others or yourself – avoid sycophancy.
6. Do not place absolute trust in others any more than in yourself – question authorities and your own convictions.
7. Seek what is essential – embed observations within a coherent system of knowledge.
8. Build something better, do not look for scapegoats – think constructively.

9. Do not generalize too hastily – the euphoria of generalization obscures counterexamples.
10. Avoid relying on clichés and ready-made formulas – stereotypical phrases are an escape from justification.

These rules strip debate of the emotional "charms of the ring," but they represent the cost of authentic understanding.

I think an attentive reader, after reviewing this decalogue, might say: great, but what does it have to do with anything? Paraphrasing Grzegorzczyk, one might ask about the meaning of the described attitude. This decalogue is not the starting point for inquiries into values, but rather describes the intellectual effort necessary to understand Grzegorzczyk's argumentation. Nowadays, it is relatively easy to describe a philosopher's views. However, making fundamental decisions through quotes from the philosopher's works is not a rational strategy. One might conclude from isolated quotations that the philosopher defended psychologism and endorsed reism. Yet, dictionary definitions of these philosophical terms lead us astray. Let us, therefore, try to discover the foundations of rational thinking about values. We can take the following interconnected theses as self-evident:

1. A phrase is a logical proposition if it can be examined to see whether it describes the truth (what is in reality). We can study models and abstract propositions, but when the description concerns ethics, the propositions must refer to reality. However, this does not mean that ethical propositions describe physical facts; rather, they reduce moral imperatives to concrete, real forms of interpersonal interaction.
2. Every proposition requires a predicate. Therefore, when describing abstractions or collective entities (such as society or a nation), we are describing relations. For example, like this: "In the human world, individual human beings truly exist. Meanwhile, states, classes, nations, ideas exist only to the extent that there are individuals who create, maintain, or profess them" (Grzegorzczyk, 2018). This is very

important because one cannot assume, for instance, that a nation has its own will or goals and can subordinate people to them.

3. The description of man and his morality cannot be abstracted from the sphere of human experiences. For the language in which we describe, semantics (the meaning of words) cannot be created in complete detachment from man. Andrzej Grzegorzcyk himself acknowledged that this view is a "defense of psychologism" (Krajewski, 2016), though it must be noted that this refers to semantic psychologism, rather than the logical psychologism described at the beginning. This is an important distinction, as total anti-psychologism precludes the logical analysis of values.
4. How, then, can logical argumentation be applied in a language that permits semantic psychologism? This is possible, for instance, by operating with categories or eliminating alternatives by reducing them to absurdity.

4. Radical Personalism

Once the truth is discovered, we cannot seek a compromise. If it is true about goodness, speaking of a "lesser evil" is illogical. Let us trace this using the example of the analysis of war and peace (Grzegorzcyk, 1979). Grzegorzcyk starts from human free will: war is the conscious destruction of values by people, while peace is a state of active kindness in overcoming suffering. The material world tends toward decay (what Grzegorzcyk calls an increase in "social entropy"); egoism is simpler, while altruism requires constant moral effort. Two attitudes spring from this intuition:

- **Solidary (utilitarian) ethics** allows for limiting a lesser evil, provided that a "just war" is maintained (defense of an indispensable good, exhaustion of peaceful methods).
- **Absolutist ethics** rejects any planned violation of the "thou shalt

not kill" principle; it serves as a transcendent point of reference protecting reason from relativism.

From the standpoint of utilitarian logic, if we sum up individuals, the good of the majority will always mathematically outweigh the good of the minority. The survival and high standard of living of humanity could be guaranteed by one strong nation exterminating all weaker nations and killing its own unproductive individuals. However, the human moral sense rejects such solutions as absurd. We can therefore (and indeed must) acknowledge that utilitarianism leads to *reductio ad absurdum* and is therefore internally inconsistent.

Since we reject relativism, can we - while rejecting violence (not just wars) - justify the use of force, for example, in self-defense? Here, the problem of language precision, to which Grzegorzczuk draws attention, comes to light. Our dilemmas arise from conflating different concepts. Just as in the hard sciences, the emergence of a contradiction forces the search for a new theory, so too in ethics, a contradiction cannot be resolved through compromises, but rather through the introduction of adequate concepts (a "new theory"). In this case, however, one must distinguish **violence** (the destruction of an opponent) from the use of **force** in self-defense or in defense of the weak.

Returning to the ability to perceive absurdity (regarding utilitarianism), it is worth considering where it comes from. According to the philosopher, it stems from the primacy of the spirit over matter. Through abstraction, the mind transcends biological egoism through an "intellectual-volitional mechanism of self-compulsion" - it weakens biological motives in favor of spiritual ones. There is no question, then, of hard-to-verify predispositions. Grzegorzczuk describes the deepest metaphysical intuitions using a metaphor, verified by its aptness rather than its correspondence with material facts.

5. Dignity of the Person

The rejection of utilitarianism does not suspend us in a vacuum, but - to avoid falling into contradiction - leads us deductively to adopt personalism. Let us introduce a distinction between utilitarian values and existential values. Since the utilitarian principle of the summability of humans fails, deduction compels the conclusion that **the existential value of every human being is an absolute value, incomparable to that of another human being**. This means there is no justification for subordinating one person to another. This, in turn, implies a prohibition on instrumental treatment (that is, enslavement, or to put it bluntly: subordination). We are thus left with only one option: the recognition of the absolute dignity of the person.

6. The Hierarchy of Values

From the concept of human dignity, a whole range of other values can be derived. For example, the value of **truth** follows from the fact that concealing it is a form of degradation. Opposition to evil must always be linked to exposing the truth. In turn, the **good of the community** rests on spiritual values: on the selfless gift of service, and above all, on forgiveness. Such concern for every human being can be defined as **justice**. Creating a comprehensive catalog of universal values is beyond the scope of this article. Here, I present only the method for such inquiries.

If we think of values as the foundation of law, we must find a way to capture the relationships between values that does not create problems in their application. A good approximation of these relationships is a simple hierarchy. The foundations of such a hierarchy can be found in the works of Andrzej Grzegorzczak:

1. **Absolute foundation:** The existential value of the person.
2. **Higher level of the hierarchy:** Spiritual values (autotelic goals). These include, among others:

- **Truth** (as selfless cognition and understanding).
 - **Justice, respect, kindness, and neighborly love** (which constitute the "Good of the community").
3. **Lower level of the hierarchy:** Vital values (instrumental means). Such as property, convenience, security, or institutional freedoms (e.g., property rights, political freedom of association).

Grzegorzczuk warned against treating the hierarchy mechanically and chronologically (for this reason, he explicitly criticized Maslow's pyramid of needs). In the practice of social life, Grzegorzczuk's simple principle of hierarchy boils down to two rules:

- **The principle of conflict and overriding priority:** Conflicts constantly arise between vital (lower) and spiritual (higher) values. As the philosopher writes: "Respect for all people contradicts the adoration of those who are vital to us. Justice for all opposes favoring one's own" (Grzegorzczuk, 2018). In such situations, the principle of hierarchy requires the firm subordination of property, self-interest, convenience, or particular benefit (vital values) to truth, justice, and the good of the person (spiritual values).
- **Self-mastery:** As vital values are hardwired into our physical instincts, maintaining this hierarchy requires deliberate effort. It calls for **self-imposed** pressure - driven by willpower and discipline - to make the lower serve the higher.

7. Application of the Method in the Era of Algorithms

The significance of this method becomes apparent in an era in which life is increasingly automated (in financial decisions, law, and administration). Contemporary liberal democracies, which assume a pluralism of values, find it difficult to construct rules for machines that require unambiguous

guidelines. There appears to be a need to move from general declarations to their formal analysis.

Grzegorzczuk's method enables this transition. If values are a discovered order, their mutual relationships can be investigated. The dignity of the person becomes an axiom from which truth, justice, and freedom follow. If values remain in logical relations, they can act as a semantic constraint for the legal system. Law becomes a structure in which any new norm must pass a test of consistency with the system's axiological core.

The algorithmization of law does not mean handing over power to machines, but rather subordinating both sides to common principles. The role of technology is to detect logical inconsistencies, while man takes responsibility for them. This allows for the creation of a shared axiology - a law resilient against relativism and technocratic reductionism.

8. Conclusion

In this sense, Grzegorzczuk's method may prove to be one of the most important philosophical tools of the 21st century. It preserves the central place of the human person in a world of algorithms, subordinating technology to human dignity. This opens the path to a social order that protects values.

Man actively co-creates the moral order. Cognition is an effort to save our humanity; through the algorithmization of legal structures, we ensure that humans and machines share the same values. This leads neither to the humanization of machines nor to the reduction of man. The law constitutes a space that eliminates conflicts among humans and between humans and machines, operating within a common framework of rational, human-centered law.

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